

Collaborative autoethnography on third space identity

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In many universities, traditional academics experience a clear sense of belonging due to the alignment between their professional identity and their discipline. However, third space professionals often struggle to find their place in the university setting.

Research has highlighted the unique position of third space practitioners, who occupy a liminal space (Bhabha, 2004) within the higher education landscape. These practitioners often feel “homeless” and have a vague sense of belonging. Their roles are described as liminal, binary/overlap, or borderless. Despite their expertise in teaching and learning, they are often perceived as “lesser” than discipline-based academics and professional staff.

This presentation explored research stemming from a collaborative auto-ethnographic study. In this study, three third space practitioners reflected on their professional identities, their roles in supporting academics, the assumptions they bring to their work, and their interactions with others. The presenting team also shared the challenges they faced in getting this research off the ground owing to the volatile nature of third space academic roles.

Reflection

It was heartening to hear feedback from others during the session about how the themes we uncovered in our research resonated with many of them. Many participants shared their own challenging experiences related to these themes.

Reference

Bhabha, H. (2004). *The location of culture* (2nd ed.), Routledge.

About the authors

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